

Module: ARCH3100
Human Osteoarchaeology
Class Time: Tues. 2–3 PM
Thurs. 2–4 PM
Location: Ardmore Seminar
Room/Teaching Lab
Office Hours: Mon. 9–11 AM
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
Contributions from:
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Santiago Caruso – Wunderkammer

Module Description

Knowledge of human osteology is key for fields such as archaeology, biological anthropology, forensic anthropology, anatomy, and medicine. This course introduces students to human skeletal anatomy and the field of osteoarchaeology, the study of human skeletal remains from archaeological sites. The first half of the course introduces skeletal anatomy for anthropologists and archaeologists and covers the entire human skeleton, with sections on growth, development, and pathology. The skeletal anatomy of select fauna will be used to demonstrate the functional morphology of each bone. This second half of the course introduces students to the basic methods of human skeletal analysis, including assessing the age, sex, health, and stature of an individual using their bones. Overall, the module will highlight how osteoarchaeology can aid archaeologists in reconstructing key aspects of past lives—including identity and lived experiences of diet, trauma, and mobility—and contribute to our understanding of what it means to be human, in both the past and the present.

Learning Outcomes

Upon completion of this module, students should be able to:

- Identify individual bones and recognise key skeletal features
- Distinguish human and non-human bones
- Estimate age, sex, stature, and Minimum Number of Individuals (MNI) from human remains
- Understand how osteoarchaeology can illuminate the identity and lived experiences of people in the past

Class Behavior

This class includes handling casts of human bones and looking at images of dead bodies. All students are expected to maintain high levels of professionalism in this course, which includes respect for the dead and for each other. You may not take personal photos of the casts or handle food or drink while in the Archaeology Teaching Lab. Any disrespectful behaviors will result in a penalty on your overall course grade and may result in removal from the course.

Readings

The optional textbook is Steele and Bramblett (1988) *The Anatomy and Biology of the Human Skeleton*. Additional readings will be posted on the course Brightspace page under “My Learning”, organized by week.

There are two copies of the optional textbook in the UCD library. If you do not want to use the optional textbook, there will be weekly handouts detailing the bones, features, and information you will need to learn for assessments. There are many resources available online that can help provide clarity and guidance for identifying bones and features (some of which are listed at the end of this syllabus). Finally, pdfs of class lecture slides will be posted for every meeting, which can also be used as guides.

School of Archaeology Culture

UCD School of Archaeology is committed to creating an environment where diversity is celebrated and everyone is treated fairly, regardless of gender, age, race, disability, ethnic origin, religion, sexual orientation, civil status, family status or membership of the travelling community. The School is also committed to the promotion of a study environment that upholds the dignity and respect of the individual and that supports every individual's right to study in an environment free of any form of harassment, intimidation or bullying. For further information and supports, please visit <http://www.ucd.ie/archaeology/edi>

Supports

This module is supported by materials on Brightspace, including readings, the syllabus, assessment guidelines, and other additional resources.

Contacting the module coordinator

If you have any queries and would like to speak to me individually, my open office hours during Autumn 2024 are Mondays from 9:00–11:00 AM in my office, Newman K011a. Office hours are cancelled for Monday, November 16, as I am teaching into another module in the School of Archaeology. For other times, please email me to arrange an appointment. You are also welcome to approach me before or after lectures. Alternatively, I am happy to deal with any queries you may have by email.

[For School Office details and contacts, please click here >>](#)

Times

The module runs:

- Mondays 2:00–3:00 PM, meeting in the Ardmore Annexe seminar room,
- Tuesdays, 2:00–4:00 PM. Meeting in the Ardmore Annexe seminar room, moving to the teaching lab for practical periods unless otherwise noted.

Schedule of Course Meetings

Practicals are self-directed structured study time where Dr Beck will circulate and answer questions to help you identify and side elements and identify landmarks. Practical time can also be used to work on your bone notebooks. *Labs* are meetings focused on developing methodological skills and will ask you to move through structured stations and fill out worksheets, working as a group. Please note that topics describe lecture topics. The practicals will cover everything discussed in lectures for that week.

Meeting	Date	Category	Topic
1.1	Mon. 9 Sept.	Lecture	Anatomical Terminology, Bone Biology & Ethics
1.2	Tues. 10 Sept.	Lecture + Practical	The Skull
2.1	Mon. 16 Sept.	Lecture	The Teeth
2.2	Tues. 17 Sept.	Practical	
3.1	Mon. 23 Sept.	Lecture	The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle
3.2	Tues. 24 Sept.	Practical	
4.1	Mon. 30 Sept.	Lecture	The Arm & Forearm
4.2	Tues. 1 Oct.	Lecture + Practical	The Wrist
5.1	Mon. 7 Oct.	Lecture	The Hand & Fingers
5.2	Tues. 8 Oct.	Lecture + Practical	The Pelvic Girdle
6.1	Mon. 14 Oct.	Open Review	Open Review for A1
6.2	Tues. 15 Oct.	Assessment	Assessment 1
7.1*	Mon. 21 Oct	Lecture	The Lower Limb
7.2*	Tues. 22 Oct.	Lecture + Practical	Growth, Development & Pathology Lower Limb Practical
WEEK 8 = SCHOOL OF ARCHAEOLOGY READING WEEK: NO CLASS			
9.1	Mon. 4 Nov.	Lecture	Estimating Adult Age
9.2	Tues. 5 Nov.	Lecture + Lab	Estimating Subadult Age Age Estimation Lab
10.1	Mon. 11 Nov.	Lecture	Assessing Sex
10.2	Tues. 12 Nov.	Lab + Practical	Assessment of Sex Lab Practical
11.1	Mon. 18 Nov.	Lecture	Stature + Trauma, Taphonomy, MNI
11.2	Tues. 19 Nov.	Lecture + Lab	Comparative Functional Anatomy Comparative Anatomy Lab
12.1	Mon. 25 Nov.	Open Review	Open Review for A2
12.2	Tues. 26 Nov.	Assessment	Assessment 2

*Meetings led by María Serrano Ruber

Class Schedule and Reading List

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change this schedule if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course.

Week 1: Anatomical Terminology, Bone Biology & Ethics + The Skull I

Monday, 9 September

Lecture: Bone Biology, Anatomical Terminology & Ethics

Reading(s): None

Tuesday, 10 September

Lecture: The Skull

Practical: The Skull I

Reading(s): Bernstein, 2018; Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 1: Introduction to the Study of the Human Skeleton + Chapter 2: Bone Biology (16 pp.)

Week 2: The Skull II + The Teeth

Monday, 16 September

Lecture: The Teeth

Reading(s): None

Tuesday, 17 September

Practical: The Skull II + The Teeth

Reading(s): Bone Broke: [Identifying Human Teeth](#); White & Folkens 2005, Chapter 8: Dentition, pp.127–152 (26 pp.)

Week 3: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Monday, 23 September

Lecture: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 5: The Vertebral Column (26 pp.)

Tuesday, 24 September

Practical: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 6: The Chest and Shoulder Girdle (41 pp.)

Week 4: The Arm & Forearm + The Wrist

Monday, 30 September

Lecture: The Arm & Forearm + The Wrist

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 7: The Arm (19 pp.)

Tuesday, 1 October

Practical: The Arm, Forearm & Wrist

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 8: The Wrist, Hand, and Fingers (16 pp.)

Week 5: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Monday, 7 October

Lecture: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 9: The Pelvic Girdle (25 pp.)

Tuesday, 8 October

Practical: The Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Reading(s): None

Week 6: Open Review + Assessment 1

Monday, 14 October

Open review in teaching lab

Tuesday, 15 October

ASSESSMENT 1

Week 7: The Lower Limb

Monday, 21 October

Lecture: The Lower Limb

Optional Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 10: The Leg (26 pp.); Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 11: The Ankle, Foot, and Toes (20 pp.)

Tuesday, 22 October

Lecture: Growth, Development & Pathology

Practical: The Lower Limb

Reading(s): None

WEEK 8: SoA READING WEEK, NO CLASSES

Week 9: Estimating Age + Estimation of Age Lab

Monday, 4 November

Lecture: Estimating Subadult Age

Reading(s): Scheuer and Black, 2004 (22 pp.)

Tuesday, 5 November

Lecture: Estimating Adult Age

Lab: Estimation of Age

Reading(s): Byers, 2017, Chapter 9: Estimation of Age at Death (pp.218–236)

Week 10: Assessing Sex + Assessment of Sex Lab

Monday, 11 November

Lecture: Assessing Sex

Reading(s): Stone, 2012 (3 pp.)

Optional Reading(s): Hollimon, 2011 (14 pp.)

Tuesday, 12 November

Lab: Assessment of Sex

Open Review Period

Reading(s): White and Folkens, 2005, Chapter 19: Determination of Sex (pp.386–398).

Week 11: Estimating Stature & Assessing Taphonomy, Trauma & MNI + Comparative Anatomy

Monday, 18 November

Lecture: Estimating Stature, Evaluating Trauma, Taphonomy, and MNI

Reading(s): Byers 2008, Chapter 8: Estimation of Stature, pp.250–269 (19 pp.)

Optional Reading(s): Beck et al., 2015 (10 pp.)

Tuesday, 19 November

Lecture: Comparative Functional Anatomy

Lab: Comparative Functional Anatomy

Optional Reading(s): Beisaw, 2013 (55 pp.)

Week 12: Open Review + Assessment 2

Monday, 25 November

Open review in teaching lab

Tuesday, 26 November

ASSESSMENT 2

Assessment

	Assignment	%	Nature	Date
1	Assessment 1	35%	In class assessment	Tuesday, 15 October 2024
2	Bone Notebook	30%	Cumulative work over trimester	Tuesday, 19 November 2024
3	Assessment 2	35%	In class assessment	Tuesday, 26 November 2024

Assignment Submission

Assessment 1 and Assessment 2 will be conducted during module meeting periods. A hard copy of your Bone Notebook is due on Tuesday, 19 November 2024, unless you have received Dr Beck's permission to work in a digital medium.

[For Late Submission & extenuating circumstances procedures, please click here >>](#)

Grading Structure

Bone Notebook (30%): Sketching individual elements from several different views is a key strategy that helps novice osteologists identify features while increasing their familiarity with the human skeleton. Time will be set aside to sketch the bones or teeth we are learning; these notebooks will also act as useful repositories for identification and siding tricks and as comprehensive notes for review before exams. At the end of the course, your notebooks will be collected and graded. A detailed guide to your bone notebooks is provided on the first day of class and is available as a pdf on Brightspace.

Assessments (35% each): There will be 2 exam-style assessments in this course; the assessments will incorporate a variety of question formats, including visual identification and/or siding of bones and features, multiple choice, and written responses. The exams are worth 35% each.

Reading List

- Beck, J., I. Ostericher, G. Sollish & De León, J. (2015). Animal scavenging and scattering and the implications for documenting the deaths of undocumented border crossers in the Sonoran Desert. *Journal of Forensic Sciences* 60(S1): S11–S20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1556-4029.12597>
- Beisaw, A. M. (2013). What bone is it? In *Identifying and interpreting animal bones: A manual* (pp. 47–102). Texas A&M University Press.
- Bernstein, R. E. (2018, May 18). The skeleton in my closet. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/05/18/well/family/the-skeleton-in-my-closet.html>
- Byers, S. N. (2017). *An introduction to forensic anthropology*. 5th Ed. Routledge.
- Buikstra, J. E., & Ubelaker, D.H. (Eds.). (1994). *Standards for data collection from human skeletal remains*. Arkansas Archaeological Survey Research Series No. 44. Arkansas Archaeological Survey.
- Hollimon, S.E. (2011). Sex and gender in bioarchaeological research: Theory, method, and interpretation. In S. C. Agarwal & B. A. Glencross (Eds.). *Social bioarchaeology* (pp. 149–182). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Scheuer, L., & Black, S. (2004). Juvenile skeletal remains: Provenance, identification, and interpretation. In *The juvenile skeleton* (pp. 1–22). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Steele, D.G., & Bramblett, C.A. (1988). *The anatomy and biology of the human skeleton*. Texas A&M University Press.
- Stone, P. K. (2012). A bioarchaeology of sex and gender: What is the difference and why is it important? *The SAA Archaeological Record* 12(2),38–40.
- White, T. D., & Folkens, P. A. (2005). *The human bone manual*. Elsevier Academic Press.

Bone Broke Blog (www.bonebroke.org)

When I was in grad school and had a little more time and a lot more energy, I maintained a blog. The blog contains a vast repository of osteological and osteoarchaeological information. I still return to some of my siding and identification posts when I am in the field and refreshing my own osteological knowledge. I have identified relevant posts below, categorized by topic or anatomical region.

Anatomical Terminology

Standard Anatomical Position: [Bioarch Vocab: SAP](#)

Abduction and Adduction: [Bioarch Vocab: Abduction and Adduction](#)

Supination: [Bioarch Vocab: Supination](#)

Features and Pathology

Glenoid fossa: Bioarch Vocab: [Glenoid Fossa](#)

Nutrient foramen: [Bioarch Vocab: Nutrient Foramen](#)

Caries: Bioarch Vocab: [Caries](#)

Calculus: [Bioarch Vocab: Calculus](#)

Skull + Teeth

Splanchnocranium: [Bioarch Vocab: Splanchnocranium](#)

Temporal: [Osteomenagerie 3: The petrous portion of the temporal bone](#)

Temporal: [Palpable anatomy: How to identify and side an isolated zygomatic process](#)

Parietals: [How to identify and side parietal bones](#)

All teeth: [Identifying human teeth: Human dentition cheat sheet](#)

Vertebral Column

Vertebrae: [Osteomenagerie 7: The Vertebrae](#)

Vertebrae: [Cake or...superior articular facets?](#)

Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Ribs: [Orienting and siding regular ribs](#)

Pelvic Girdle

Innominate: [Hip hip hooray: Orienting and identifying features of the os coxae](#)

Arm, Wrist & Hand

Humerus: [Feeling shafted? Tips for identifying humeral shaft fragments](#)

Radius: [That's so rad: Identifying and siding the radius](#)

Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)

Scaphoid: [Osteomenagerie 2: The scaphoid](#)

Lunate: [In Honor of the "Super Moon" – Identifying and siding the lunate](#)

Carpals: [Osteomenagerie 4: The capitate](#)

Pisiform: [Osteomenagerie 5: The pisiform](#)

Hamate: [Identifying and siding the hamate](#)

Leg, Ankle & Foot

Tibia: [Tibial pursuit: How to identify and side the tibia](#)

Femur: [Get a leg up on the competition: Tips for identifying femoral shaft fragments](#)

Patella: [A guide to quickly siding the patella](#)

Navicular: [Osteomenagerie 1: The navicular](#)

Calcaneus: [Osteomenagerie 6: Tips for siding the calcaneus](#)

Cuneiforms: [Merely a cuneiformality: Identifying and siding the cuneiforms](#)

Pedal Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)

Virtual Resources

These are resources you can use to hone and practice your skills outside of lab.

John Hawks Laboratory (UW Madison)
– Virtual Labs in Biological Anthropology

JOHN HAWKS LABORATORY
Human evolution and genetics

<https://hominin.anthropology.wisc.edu/virtual-labs.html>

A variety of virtual anthropology labs are available on this website, which is of particular utility for students interested in biological anthropology and paleoanthropology. The first five labs—Regions of the Skeleton, Regions of the Cranium, Morphology of the Femur, Morphology of the Pelvis, and Pelvic Sexual Dimorphism—are useful resources.

eSkeletons (University of Texas at Austin)

<http://eskeletons.org/>

eSkeletons is an online osteology database aimed at teaching skeletal anatomy. It allows you to filter by species, specimen, bone, and view. This is an excellent resource for the comparative anatomy of primates. For example, if you want to compare photographs of a human hamate (one of the bones in the wrist) to a gibbon hamate, you can easily do so using the eSkeletons database.

Digitized Diseases (University of Bradford)

<http://www.digitiseddiseases.org/alpha/>

“an open access resource featuring human bones which have been digitised using 3D laser scanning, CT and radiography. The resource focuses on a wide range of pathological type specimens from archaeological and historical medical collections, specifically examples of chronic diseases which affect the human skeleton for which many of the physical changes are often not directly observable within clinical practice. [Includes] high fidelity photo-realistic digital representations of 3D bones that can be viewed, downloaded and manipulated on their computer, tablet or smartphone.” This is fantastic for students interested in bioarchaeology, especially skeletal pathology and trauma. Caveat: As of February, 2021 the site was experiencing some glitches due to a server upgrade.

Morphosource (Duke University)

<https://www.morphosource.org/>

Morphosource compiles 2D and 3D data from a variety of museums, researchers, and colleges for a wide variety of species. As of February 2021, Morphosource has 235 human scans, and you can zoom and rotate the scans in their online portal. For quick reference, here is the taxonomic categorization of humans:

Kingdom–Animalia | Phylum–Chordata | Class–Mammalia | Order–Primates

Family–Hominidae | Genus–Homo | Species–sapiens

Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History 3D Collection

<https://3d.si.edu/collections/hominin-fossils>

Smithsonian
National Museum of Natural History

The Smithsonian has a 3D collection of CT or laser-scanned artifacts, fossils, and animals that you can view, rotate, and interact with on their website. The full collection can be found here <https://humanorigins.si.edu/evidence/3d-collection>, and the hominin fossils are linked above. The fossil scans are all of crania or mandibles, and there are a few specimens of Homo sapiens in the collection. This is a good site for students interested in biological anthropology, particularly paleoanthropology.

The Radiologist Instagram Page

<https://www.instagram.com/theradiologistpage>

Dr Naveen Sharma—a UK-based Consultant Radiologist—provides a resource that helps anyone learn more about radiology. Radiographs are labelled in detail, and there are lots of memes! This is a useful resource for students considering pre-med or a career in radiology.

**Human Osteology Resources
(Wichita State University)**

**WICHITA STATE
UNIVERSITY**

<https://libraries.wichita.edu/c.php?g=120021&p=782022>

This library page lists a variety of resources for learning osteology and can be used to further your interests in anatomy, human biology, paleopathology, and radiology.